

Fourth Teopltiz Determinant for Analytic Function Defined by Gegenbauer Polynomial involving the Sine function

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Abstract

In this work, a new class of analytic function was defined by the Gegenbauer polynomial involving the sine function. The initial coefficient estimates were obtained and the fourth Toeplitz determinants was presented.

Keywords: Analytic function, Sine function, Gegenbauer polynomial, Toeplitz determinant.

MSC2010: 30C45.

1 Introduction

Orthogonal polynomials were discovered by Legendre in 1784 [1]. Under specific model restrictions, orthogonal polynomials are frequently employed to discover solutions of ordinary differential equations. Moreover, orthogonal polynomials are a critical feature in approximation theory. Two polynomials P_n and P_m , of order n and m , respectively, are orthogonal if

$$\langle P_n, P_m \rangle = \int_c^d P_n(x)P_m(x)r(x)dx = 0$$

for $n \neq m$ where $r(x)$ is non-negative function in the interval (c, d) ; therefore, all finite order polynomials $P_n(x)$ have well-defined integral. An example of an orthogonal polynomial is a Gegenbauer polynomial (GP) [2]. Several authors have carried out research on the Gegenbauer polynomial, see [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] and [9].

Many researchers have studied several Hankel and Toeplitz determinants for various classes of functions. For example, Janteng et al. [10] investigated second Hankel determinant for a function with a positive real part and starlike and convex functions, respectively; Bansal [11], Lee et al. [12] and Shaharuddin et al [13] discussed the second Hankel determinant for certain analytic functions; Zaprawa [14], Zhang et al. [15] and Babalola [16] derived third-order Hankel determinant for certain different univalent functions; Raza and Malik. [17] and Shi et al. [18], [19], and Breaz et al [20], studied upper bounds of the third Hankel determinant for some classes of analytic functions related

to lemniscate of Bernoulli, cardioid domain and exponential function; Mahmood et al. [21] found third Hankel determinant for a subclass of q -starlike functions. Following the above work, Zhang et al. [22] recently considered fourth-order Hankel determinants of starlike functions related to the sine function. On the other hand, Ramachandran and Kavitha [23] and Ali et al. [24] studied Toeplitz matrices whose elements are the coefficients of starlike, close-to-convex, and univalent functions. Besides, Tang et al., [25] studied third-order Hankel and Toeplitz determinant for a subclass of multivalent q -starlike functions of order α ; Zhang et al. [26] considered third-order Hankel and Toeplitz determinants of starlike functions, which are defined by using the sine function; Ramachandran et al. [27] derived an estimation for the Hankel and Toeplitz determinant with domains bounded by conical sections involving Ruscheweygh derivative; Srivastava et al. [28] found the Hankel determinant and the Toeplitz matrices for a newly defined class of analytic q -starlike functions. Motivated by the work of Al-Hawary et al [2], Al-Shbeil et al [8], Olatunji et al [29] and Zhang and Tang [30], it is established that Gegenbauer polynomial also promotes the advancement of geometric function theory. In this paper, we aim to investigate the second, third and fourth-order Toeplitz determinant for this function class $K_{\mu,s}$ associated with sine function and obtain the upper bounds for the determinants.

2 Preliminaries

Let \mathbb{A} denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k \quad (2.1)$$

in the unit disk \mathbb{D} , $\mathbb{D} = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| \leq 1\}$.

which are analytic in the unit disc \mathbb{D} with conditions $f(0) = f'(0) - 1 = 0$. Recall that, \mathbb{S} is representing a univalent function with some of the above conditions. With simple modification and differentiation, various subclasses of \mathbb{A} are known such as starlike function, convex function, close-to-convex just to mention but a few with representations below [31].

[32] A function $f(z) \in \mathbb{A}$ is said to be starlike if it satisfies the condition

$$\Re \left(\frac{z f'(z)}{f(z)} \right) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

Denote this class by \mathcal{S}^* .

[32] A function $f(z) \in \mathbb{A}$ is said to be convex if it satisfies the condition

$$\Re \left(1 + \frac{z f''(z)}{f'(z)} \right) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

Denote this class by \mathcal{C} .

[32] A function $f(z) \in \mathbb{A}$ is called close-to-convex, if there exist a convex function ϕ such that

$$\Re \left(\frac{f'(z)}{\phi'(z)} \right) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

Kaplan's definition does not require that the function ϕ is normalized, but since the majority of results obtained for close-to-convex functions assume this, we will suppose that ϕ so that $\phi(0) = 0$ and $\phi'(0) = 1$.

1001[32],1001[33],1001[34] and 1001[35]. A function $f(z) \in \mathbb{A}$ is called close-to-convex, if there exist a function $g \in \mathcal{S}^*$ such that

$$\Re \left(\frac{f'(z)}{g(z)} \right) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

Denote this class by \mathcal{K}_\circ . Choosing $g(z) = f(z)$, it is clear that $\mathcal{S}^* \subset \mathcal{K}_\circ$ and so $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{S}^* \subset \mathcal{K}_\circ$. [32] Let ρ be analytic in \mathbb{D} , with $\rho(0) = 1$. Denote by P the class of functions ρ with Taylor series expansion

$$\rho(z) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} d_n z^n \quad (2.2)$$

satisfying

$$\Re(\rho(z)) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

(Derek *et al.*, 2018). Functions in P are referred to as functions with positive real parts in \mathbb{D} or Caratheodory functions. [32] For two functions f and g analytic in \mathbb{U} , we say that the function $f(z)$ is subordinate to $g(z)$ in \mathbb{U} and write

$$f(z) \prec g(z) \quad (2.3)$$

($z \in \mathbb{U}$) if there exists a Schwartz function $w(z)$ analytic in \mathbb{U} with $w(0) = 0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$ ($z \in \mathbb{U}$) such that

$$f(z) = g(w(z))$$

In particular, if the function g is univalent in \mathbb{U} , the above subordination is equivalent to $f(0) = g(0)$ and $f(\mathbb{U}) \subset g(\mathbb{U})$.

For non-zero real constant λ , a generating function of Gegenbauer polynomials.

$$\kappa_\lambda(m, z) = \frac{1}{(1 - 2mz + z^2)^\lambda}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $m \in [-1,1]$ and $z \in U$. For fixed m the function $\kappa_{\lambda,m}$ is analytic in U , so it can be expanded on a Taylor series as

$$\kappa_{\lambda,m} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n^\lambda(m) z^n, \quad (2.5)$$

where $C_n^\lambda(m)$ is Gegenbauer polynomial of degree n .

Obviously κ_λ generates nothing when $\lambda = 0$. Therefore, the generating function of the Gegenbauer polynomial is set to be

$$\kappa_0(m, z) = 1 - \log(1 - 2mz + z^2) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n^0(m) z^n \quad (2.6)$$

for $\lambda = 0$ and Gegenbauer polynomials can also be defined by the following recurrence relations:

$$C_n^\lambda(m) = \frac{1}{n} [2m(n + \lambda - 1)C_{n-1}^\lambda(m) - (n + 2\lambda - 2)C_{n-1}^\lambda(m)] \quad (2.7)$$

with initial values

$$C_0^\lambda(m) = 1, C_1^\lambda(m) = 2\lambda m, C_2^\lambda(m) = 2\lambda(1 + \lambda)m^2 - \lambda$$

$$\text{and } C_3^\lambda(m) = \frac{4\lambda(\lambda + 1)(\lambda + 2)}{3}m^2 - 2\lambda(\lambda + 1)m \quad (2.8)$$

see details in [36]

Szynał [37] introduced the class $T(\lambda)$ as a subclass consisting of functions of the form

$$c(z) = \int_{-1}^1 k(z, m) d\sigma(m) \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$k(z, m) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} c_{n-1}^{\lambda}(m)z^n \quad (2.10)$$

Let

$$\zeta_{\lambda, m}f(z) = k(z, m) * f = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} c_{n-1}^{\lambda}(m)a_n z^n \quad (2.11)$$

(2.11) denotes the Hadarmard product of (2.1) and (2.10).

To prove our desired results, we require the following lemmas and definitions.

Lemma 2.1. [30]. If $p(z) \in P$ from 2.2, then $|d_n| \leq 2, n = 1, 2, \dots$

Lemma 2.2. [30] Let $p(z) \in P$, then $2d_2 = d_1^2 + (4 - d_1^2)\xi$. and $4d_3 = d_1^3 + 2d_1(4 - d_1^2)\xi - d_1(4 - d_1^2)\xi^2 + 2(4 - d_1^2)(1 - |\xi|^2)\eta$. for some ξ, η satisfying $|\xi| \leq 1, |\eta| \leq 1$ and $d_1 \in [0, 2]$.

Lemma 2.3. [30] If $p(z) \in P$, then

$$|d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2}| \leq 2 - \frac{|d_1^2|}{2}, \quad (2.12)$$

$$|d_{n+k} - \mu d_n d_k| < 2, 0 \leq \mu \leq 1 \quad (2.13)$$

$$|d_{n+2k} - \mu d_n d_k^2| \leq 2(1 + 2\mu). \quad (2.14)$$

Lemma 2.4. [36]. If $g(z) \in S^*$, then $|b_n| \leq n, n \geq 2$.

[32] Let ρ be analytic in \mathbb{D} , with $p(0) = 1$. Denote by P the class of functions ρ with Taylor series expansion

$$\rho(z) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} d_n z^n \quad (2.15)$$

satisfying

$$\Re(\rho(z)) > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{D}).$$

(Derek et al., 2018).

Now we define the following new subclass of $K_{\mu, s}$ as follows [30]. Let $\zeta_{\lambda, m} \in K_{\mu, s}$, if $\zeta_{\lambda, m} \in A$ and there exists $g(z) \in S^*$ such that

$$\left| \frac{z(\zeta_{\lambda, m}f)'(z)}{g(z)} - 1 \right| < \sin z$$

where $\lambda \geq 0, m \in [1, -1]$ and $K_{\mu, s}$ denotes the natural close- to-convex analogue of S_{μ}^* . Note that s denotes the Sine function.

3 Main Results

Theorem 3.1. If $\zeta_{\lambda, m} \in K_{\mu, s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, then

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{3}{2|c_1^{\lambda}(m)|}$$

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{5}{3|c_2^{\lambda}(m)|}$$

$$|a_4| \leq \frac{53}{24|c_3^{\lambda}(m)|}$$

$$|a_5| \leq \frac{92}{15|c_4^{\lambda}(m)|}$$

Proof: From Definition 2.8, $g(z) \in S^*$ and according to subordination relationship, there exists a Schwarz function $w(z)$ with $w(0) = 0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$ such that

$$\left| \frac{z(\zeta_{\lambda,m}f)'(z)}{g(z)} - 1 \right| < \sin z$$

$$z(\zeta_{\lambda,m}f)'(z) = g(z)(1 + \sin \omega(z))$$

$$\zeta_{\lambda,m}f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} c_{n-1}^{\lambda}(m)a_n z^n$$

$$\zeta_{\lambda,m}f'(z) = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n c_{n-1}^{\lambda}(m)a_n z^{n-1}$$

$$z\zeta_{\lambda,m}f'(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n c_{n-1}^{\lambda}(m)a_n z^n \tag{3.1}$$

Now, if $g(z) \in S^*$

$$g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} b_n z^n \tag{3.2}$$

$$\exists p(z) = \frac{1 + \omega}{1 - \omega} = 1 + d_1 z + d_2 z^2 + \dots \text{such that } p(z) \in P$$

and

$$\omega(z) = \frac{p(z) - 1}{1 + p(z)} = \frac{d_1 z + d_2 z^2 + \dots}{2 + d_1 z + d_2 z^2 + \dots}$$

$$\Rightarrow \omega(z) = \frac{d_1}{2} z + \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} \right) z^2 + \left(\frac{d_1^3}{8} - \frac{d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} \right) z^3$$

$$+ \left(\frac{3d_1^2 d_2}{8} - \frac{d_1 d_3}{2} - \frac{d_1^4}{16} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} + \frac{d_4}{2} \right) z^4 + \dots$$

$$(\omega(z))^3 = \left(\frac{1}{48} d_1^3 \right) z^3 + \left(\frac{d_2 d_1^2}{16} - \frac{d_1^4}{32} \right) z^4 + \left(\frac{3d_3 d_1^2}{8} - \frac{3d_2 d_1^3}{4} + \frac{d_1 d_2^2}{4} + \frac{3d_1^5}{16} \right) z^5 \dots$$

$$(\omega(z))^5 = \frac{d_1^5}{32} z^5$$

$$\sin \omega(z) = \omega(z) - \frac{\omega(z)^3}{3!} + \frac{\omega(z)^5}{5!} + \dots$$

Substituting for $\omega(z)$ in $\sin \omega(z)$,

$$\sin \omega(z) = \frac{d_1}{2} z + \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} \right) z^2 + \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} - \frac{d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} \right) z^3 + \left(\frac{5d_1^2 d_2}{16} - \frac{d_1 d_3}{2} - \frac{3d_1^4}{32} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} + \frac{d_4}{2} \right) z^4$$

$$+ \left(\frac{5d_1^2 d_3}{16} + \frac{5d_1 d_2^2}{16} - \frac{5d_1^3 d_2}{48} + \frac{61d_1^5}{3840} - \frac{d_2 d_3}{32} + \frac{d_5}{2} + \frac{d_1 d_4}{2} \right) z^5 \dots$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 + \sin \omega(z) = & 1 + \frac{d_1}{2} z + \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} \right) z^2 + \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} - \frac{d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} \right) z^3 + \left(\frac{5d_1^2 d_2}{16} - \frac{d_1 d_3}{2} - \frac{3d_1^4}{32} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} + \frac{d_4}{2} \right) z^4 \\
 & + \left(\frac{5d_1^2 d_3}{16} + \frac{5d_1 d_2^2}{16} - \frac{5d_1^3 d_2}{48} + \frac{61d_1^5}{3840} - \frac{d_2 d_3}{32} + \frac{d_5}{2} + \frac{d_1 d_4}{2} \right) z^5 \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplied by $(g(z))$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 g(z)(1 + \sin \omega(z)) = & z + \left(\frac{d_1}{2} + b_2 \right) z^2 + \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} + \frac{d_1 b_2}{2} + b_3 \right) z^3 \\
 & + \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} - \frac{d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{d_2 b_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2 b_2}{4} + \frac{d_1 b_3}{2} + b_4 \right) z^4 + \dots \quad (3.3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equating coefficients (3.1) and (3.3); we have that

$$(2c_1^\lambda(m)a_2) z^2 = \left(\frac{d_1}{2} + b_2 \right) z^2 \quad (3.4)$$

$$(3c_2^\lambda(m)a_3) z^3 = \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} + \frac{d_1 b_2}{2} + b_3 \right) z^3 \quad (3.5)$$

$$(4c_3^\lambda(m)a_4) z^4 = \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} - \frac{d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{d_2 b_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2 b_2}{4} + \frac{d_1 b_3}{2} + b_4 \right) z^4 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (5c_4^\lambda(m)a_5) z^5 = & \left(\frac{5d_1^2 d_2}{16} + \frac{d_4}{2} - \frac{d_1 d_3}{2} - \frac{3d_1^4}{32} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} + \frac{5d_1^3 b_2}{48} - \frac{b_2 d_1 d_2}{2} + \frac{d_1 b_4}{2} + \frac{b_2 d_3}{2} + \frac{b_3 d_2}{2} - \frac{b_3 d_1^2}{4} + b_5 \right) z^5 \\
 & \quad (3.7)
 \end{aligned}$$

From equation 3.4

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_2 &= \frac{1}{2c_1^\lambda(m)} \left(\frac{d_1}{2} + b_2 \right) \\
 |a_2| &\leq \frac{1}{2|c_1^\lambda(m)|} \left| \frac{d_1}{2} + b_2 \right| \\
 |a_2| &\leq \left| \frac{d_1}{4|c_1^\lambda(m)|} + \frac{b_2}{2|c_1^\lambda(m)|} \right|
 \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

From equation 3.5

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_3 &= \frac{1}{3c_2^\lambda(m)} \left(\frac{d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2}{4} + \frac{d_1 b_2}{2} + b_3 \right) \\
 a_3 &= \frac{1}{3c_2^\lambda(m)} \frac{1}{2} \left(d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2} + \frac{d_1 b_2}{2} + b_3 \right) \\
 |a_3| &\leq \left| \frac{1}{3c_2^\lambda(m)} \right| \left| \frac{1}{2} \left(d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{d_1 b_2}{2} + b_3 \right| \\
 |a_3| &\leq \frac{1}{3|c_2^\lambda(m)|} \frac{1}{2} \left| d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2} \right| + \frac{|d_1||b_2|}{2} + |b_3| \quad (3.9)
 \end{aligned}$$

From (3.6)

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_4 &= \frac{1}{4c_3^\lambda(m)} \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} - \frac{d_1d_2}{2} + \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{d_2b_2}{2} - \frac{d_1^2b_2}{4} + \frac{d_1b_3}{2} + b_4 \right) \\
 a_4 &= \frac{1}{4c_3^\lambda(m)} \left(\frac{5d_1^3}{48} + \frac{d_1b_3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(d_3 - d_1d_2) + \frac{b_2}{2}(d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2}) + b_4 \right) \\
 |a_4| &\leq \left| \frac{1}{4c_3^\lambda(m)} \right| \left| \frac{5d_1^3}{48} + \frac{d_1b_3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(d_3 - d_1d_2) + \frac{b_2}{2}(d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2}) + b_4 \right| \\
 |a_4| &\leq \frac{1}{4|c_3^\lambda(m)|} \left(\frac{5|d_1^3|}{48} + \frac{|d_1||b_3|}{2} + \frac{1}{2}|d_3 - d_1d_2| + \frac{|b_2|}{2}|d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2}| + |b_4| \right) \tag{3.10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Immediately from (3.7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_5 &= \frac{1}{5c_4^\lambda(m)} \left(\frac{5d_1^2d_2}{16} + \frac{d_4}{2} - \frac{d_1d_3}{2} - \frac{3d_1^4}{32} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} + \frac{5d_1^3b_2}{48} - \frac{b_2d_1d_2}{2} + \frac{d_1b_4}{2} + \frac{b_2d_3}{2} + \frac{b_3d_2}{2} - \frac{b_3d_1^2}{4} + b_5 \right) \\
 |a_5| &\leq \left| \frac{1}{5c_4^\lambda(m)} \right| \left| \frac{5d_1^2d_2}{16} + \frac{d_4}{2} + \frac{5d_1^3b_2}{48} + b_5 + \frac{d_1b_4}{2} + \frac{b_2d_3}{2} + \frac{b_3d_2}{2} - \frac{d_1d_3}{2} - \frac{3d_1^4}{32} - \frac{d_2^2}{4} - \frac{b_2d_1d_2}{2} - \frac{b_3d_1^2}{4} \right| \\
 |a_5| &\leq \frac{1}{5|c_4^\lambda(m)|} \left| \frac{5d_1^2d_2}{16} + \frac{d_4}{2} + \frac{5d_1^3b_2}{48} + b_5 + \frac{d_1b_4}{2} + \frac{b_2d_3}{2} + \frac{b_3d_2}{2} \right| + |-d_1| \left| \frac{d_3}{2} + \frac{3d_1^3}{32} + \frac{b_2d_2}{2} + \frac{b_3d_1}{4} \right| + \left| -\frac{d_2^2}{4} \right| \\
 |a_5| &\leq \frac{1}{5|c_4^\lambda(m)|} \left[\frac{5|d_1^2||d_2|}{16} + \frac{|d_4|}{2} + \frac{5|d_1^3||b_2|}{48} + |b_5| + \frac{|d_1||b_4|}{2} + \frac{|b_2||d_3|}{2} + \frac{|b_3||d_2|}{2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + |d_1| \left(\frac{|d_3|}{2} + \frac{3|d_1^3|}{32} + \frac{|b_2||d_2|}{2} + \frac{|b_3||d_1|}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{4}|d_2^2| \right] \tag{3.11}
 \end{aligned}$$

If $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in C_n(z)$, then $|a_2| \leq \frac{3}{2c_1^\lambda(m)}$

Proof:

setting $n = 2$ in (3.1) yeilds (3.8) and applying lemmas 2.1 and 2.4

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{1}{2|c_1^\lambda(m)|} \left| \frac{d_1}{2} + b_2 \right|$$

the proof follows. This is the result obtained by Olatunji [29].

If $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in C_n(z)$, then

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{5}{3c_2^\lambda(m)}$$

Proof:

setting $n = 3$ in (3.1) yeilds (3.9) and applying lemmas 2.1, 2.3 and 2.4, we have

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{1}{3|c_2^\lambda(m)|} \left| \frac{1}{2} \left| d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2} \right| + \frac{|d_1||b_2|}{2} + |b_3| \right|$$

the proof follows. This is the result obtained by Olatunji [29].

If $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in C_n(z)$, then

$$|a_4| \leq \frac{53}{24|c_3^\lambda(m)|}$$

Proof:

setting $n = 4$ in (3.1) yeilds (3.10) and applying lemmas 2.1, 2.3 and 2.4, we have

$$|a_4| \leq \frac{1}{4|c_3^\lambda(m)|} \left(\frac{5|d_1^3|}{48} + \frac{|d_1||b_3|}{2} + \frac{1}{2}|d_3 - d_1d_2| + \frac{|b_2|}{2}|d_2 - \frac{d_1^2}{2}| + |b_4| \right)$$

hence the proof.

If $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in C_n(z)$, then

$$|a_5| \leq \frac{92}{15|c_4^\lambda(m)|}$$

Proof:

setting $n = 5$ in (3.1) yeilds (3.11) and applying lemmas 2.1, 2.3 and 2.4, we have

$$|a_5| \leq \frac{1}{5|c_4^\lambda(m)|} \left[\frac{5|d_1^2||d_2|}{16} + \frac{|d_4|}{2} + \frac{5|d_1^3||b_2|}{48} + |b_5| + \frac{|d_1||b_4|}{2} + \frac{|b_2||d_3|}{2} + \frac{|b_3||d_2|}{2} \right. \\ \left. + |d_1| \left(\frac{|d_3|}{2} + \frac{3|d_1^3|}{32} + \frac{|b_2||d_2|}{2} + \frac{|b_3||d_1|}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{4}|d_2^2| \right]$$

the proof follows.

Toeplitz Determinants of $K_{\mu,s}$

The Toeplitz matrix is a matrix in which each descending diagonal from left to right is constant, this means

$$T_q(n) = \begin{pmatrix} a_n & a_{n+1} & \dots & a_{n+q-1} \\ a_{n+1} & a_n & a_{n+1} & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & a_{n+1} \\ a_{n+q-1} & \dots & a_{n+1} & a_n \end{pmatrix}$$

$n \leq 1, q \leq 1$

This matrix has computational properties and appearances in various areas, 1001[23],1001[38]. In this work, assume $a_1 = 1$, then the estimates for the Toeplitz determinant in the cases of $q = 2, n = 2, q = 3, n = 1, q = 3, n = 2, q = 4, n = 1$ and $q = 4, n = 2$ of the analytic function having entries from the class $K_{\mu,s}$ is presented in the following Theorems.

Theorem 3.2. Let $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in K_{\mu,s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, and

$$T_2(2) = \begin{vmatrix} a_2 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

then

$$|a_3^2 - a_2^2| \leq \frac{9}{4|c_1^{2\lambda}(m)|} + \frac{71}{18|c_2^{2\lambda}(m)|}$$

Proof: The proof follows from equations 3.8 and 3.9

Theorem 3.3. Let $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in K_{\mu,s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, and

$$T_3(1) = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_2 & a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_2 & a_1 \end{vmatrix}$$

then,

$$|1 + 2a_2^2(a_3 - 1) - a_3^2| \leq 1 + \frac{1}{36|c_1^{2\lambda}c_2^\lambda(m)|} - \frac{5}{2|c_1^{2\lambda}(m)|} - \frac{97}{18|c_2^{2\lambda}(m)|}$$

Proof: The proof follows from (3.8),(3.9),(3.10) and (3.11)

Theorem 3.4. Let $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in K_{\mu,s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, and

$$T_3(2) = \begin{vmatrix} a_2 & a_3 & a_4 \\ a_3 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_4 & a_3 & a_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

then,

$$|2a_3^2(a_4 - a_2) - a_2a_4^2 + a_3^3| \leq \frac{|A|^3}{8|c_1^3(m)|} + \frac{|B|^2|C|}{18|c_2^{2\lambda}|c_3^\lambda(m)} + \frac{|A||B|^2}{9|c_1^\lambda||c_2^{2\lambda}(m)|} + \frac{|A||C|^2}{32|c_1^\lambda||c_3^{2\lambda}(m)|}$$

Proof: The proof follows.

Theorem 3.5. Let $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in K_{\mu,s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, and

$$T_4(1) = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & a_3 & a_4 \\ a_2 & a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_2 & a_1 & a_2 \\ a_4 & a_3 & a_2 & a_1 \end{vmatrix}$$

then,

$$\begin{aligned} &|1 - 3a_2^2 + 2a_2^2a_3 - 2a_3^2 - 2a_2^2a_3^2 + 4a_2a_3a_4 - 2a_2a_3^2a_4 - 2a_2^3a_4 + a_2^4 + a_3^4 + a_4^2 + a_2^2a_4^2| \\ &\leq 1 - \frac{3|A|^2}{4|c_1^{2\lambda}(m)|} + \frac{|A|^2|B|}{6|c_1^{2\lambda}|c_2^\lambda(m)} + \frac{2|B|^2}{9|c_2^{2\lambda}(m)|} + \frac{|A|^2|B|^2}{36|c_1^{2\lambda}|c_2^{2\lambda}(m)} + \frac{|A||B|^2|C|}{36|c_1^\lambda||c_2^{2\lambda}|c_3^\lambda(m)} \\ &\quad + \frac{|A|^3|C|}{16|c_1^3\lambda||c_3^\lambda(m)} + \frac{|C|^2}{16|c_3^{2\lambda}(m)|} + \frac{|A|^2|C|^2}{64|c_1^{2\lambda}|c_3^{2\lambda}(m)} \end{aligned}$$

Proof: The proof follows from (3.8),(3.9),(3.10) and (3.11).

Theorem 3.6. Let $\zeta_{\lambda,m} \in K_{\mu,s}$ where $m \in [1, -1]$, and

$$T_4(2) = \begin{vmatrix} a_2 & a_3 & a_4 & a_5 \\ a_3 & a_2 & a_3 & a_4 \\ a_4 & a_3 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_5 & a_4 & a_3 & a_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

then,

$$\begin{aligned} &|(a_2^2 - a_3^2)^2 + 2(a_3^2 - a_2a_4)(a_2a_4 - a_3a_5) - (a_2a_3 - a_3a_4)^2 + (a_4^2 - a_3a_5)^2 - (a_3a_4 - a_2a_5)^2| \\ &\leq \frac{|A|^4}{16|c_1^4\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|B|^4}{81|c_2^4\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|A||B||C||D|}{30|c_1^\lambda||c_2^\lambda||c_3^\lambda||c_4^\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|A||B|^2|C|}{18|c_1^\lambda||c_2^{2\lambda}|c_3^\lambda(m)} + \frac{|C|^4}{256|c_3^4\lambda(m)|} + \\ &\frac{|B|^2|D|^2}{225|c_2^{2\lambda}|c_4^2\lambda(m)} + \frac{|A|^2|B|^2}{12|c_1^2\lambda||c_2^2\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|A|^2|C|^2}{32|c_1^2\lambda||c_3^2\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|A|^2|D|^2}{100|c_1^2\lambda||c_3^2\lambda(m)|} + \frac{|B|^2|C|^2}{72|c_2^{2\lambda}|c_3^2\lambda(m)} + \\ &\quad \frac{2|B|^3|D|}{135|c_2^{2\lambda}|c_4^\lambda(m)} + \frac{|B||C|^2|D|}{120|c_2^\lambda||c_3^2\lambda||c_4^\lambda(m)} \end{aligned}$$

Proof: The proof follows from Theorem 3.1

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